

IMPACT OF FRAUD ON PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

Oyewole Johnson Stephen FCA and Eke Robert Ike PhD, FCA.

Department of Accounting and Finance, College of Social and Management Sciences, Wellspring University Benin City, Edo State.

E-mail: deby4stey@yahoo.com, robbyeke19@yahoo.com

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Abstract: *The objective of the study is to examine the impact of fraud on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study adopted the ex post factor research design, descriptive and data was gotten from annual reports of NIDIC from the period of 2006-2022. Descriptive analysis was used to summarize the data while the ordinary least squares was used to draw inference on the phenomenon studied. The result from the inferential statistics revealed that total Fraud Amount has no significant influence on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Secondly, it was found that number of reported cases of fraud has positive and significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Thirdly, the study found that total number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study came to the conclusion that number of reported cases of fraud has positive and significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. While total fraud amount and number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In line with findings the study, it was recommended that banks should always publish cases of fraud to boost the shareholders confidence in the banks, so as to improve the performance in form of deposit.*

1. Introduction

Fraud is viewed as a serious threat to people, organisations, and governments worldwide. It seems that fraud has reached catastrophic proportions in our culture, and scammers are becoming more daring, skilled, diligent, and intelligent in the ways they plan and carry out

their evil schemes (Kawugana & Faruna, 2018). The current wave of fraud in Nigeria's banking sector has humiliated the country, as evidenced by the law enforcement agencies' seeming attempts to hold those responsible. Although fraud is not specific to the Nigerian economy or the banking sector, the high frequency of fraud in

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the sector necessitates prompt attention in order to find solutions (Kolapo & Olaniyan, 2018).

Nigerians are becoming increasingly concerned about the increasing prevalence of electronic fraud, or "e-fraud," across major economic sectors. According to research, Nigeria loses an incredible 197.9 billion naira a year due to the widespread use of new mobile money, electronic banking, and electronic payment systems, which is accompanied by the prevalence of electronic fraud (Osugwu & Umeh, 2018). As recently as 19 years ago, Nonso et al., (2021) stated that even with the best efforts of many anti-graft authorities, fraudsters were still coming up with new, creative ways to commit computer fraud.

In literature there seems to be mixed findings on the impact of fraud on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. First, researchers have found mixed findings on the relationship between total fraud amount and the performance of deposit money banks. Kalapo & Olaniyan (2018); Muritala et al., (2017); Taiwo et al., (2016) found a significant negative relationship between performance of banks and fraud amount. On the other hand, the study of Ogbeide (2018) found fraud amount to be not significantly related to performance of DMBs. While, Kanu and Okarafor (2013) found a positive relationship between fraud amount and total deposit.

Secondly, on the relationship between number of reported cases and performance of deposit money banks, Offiong et al., (2016) and Taiwo et al., (2016) found a positive relationship between performance and the total number of reported

fraud cases in banks. However, this result was in contrast with Muritala et al., (2016) and Ogbeide (2018) which found a significant negative impact of reported fraud cases on performance of DMBs.

Lastly on the relationship between total number of staff involved in fraud, Kalapo & Olaniyan, (2018); Taiwo et al., (2016) found a negative relationship between the total number of staff involved in fraud cases and performance of banks. Ashamu (2014) was of the view that the number of staffs involved positively affects performance of DMBs. The findings of Muritala et al (2017) also revealed a significant positive relationship between the number of staff involved in reported fraud cases and the performance of DMBs. However, Offiong et al., (2016) reported no significant relationship between the number of staff involved in fraud cases and the performance of banks.

2. Research Questions

The following questions were asked. They are;

1. What is the impact of total fraud amount on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of number of reported cases of fraud on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria?
3. What is the effect of Total number of staff involvement in fraud on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objectives of this study is investigate the impact of fraud on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Specifically the study intends to;

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1. examine the impact of total fraud on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
2. Investigate the impact of reported cases of fraud on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
3. Determine the effect of total number of fraud staff involvement in fraud cases on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Hypothesis of the Study

The following hypothesis stated in null form will guide the study;

- i. Total fraud amount does not have significant influence on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- ii. Reported fraud cases does not have significant effect on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.
- iii. Total number of staff involved in fraud cases does not have significant influence on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Section 2: Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1. Performance of Deposit Money Banks Nigeria

The term performance has been defined by various scholars. As stated in Ifionu and Keremah (2016) defined performance as “the end result of activity and the appropriate measure selected to assess corporate performance is considered to depend on the type of organisation to be evaluated and the objective to be achieved through that evaluation. Masud and Haq (2016) defined performance has also been defined as how well an organisation uses resources at its disposal.

Traditionally, performance of banks are measured using quantitative financial ratios such as Profit before Tax (PBT), Return on Asset (ROA), Return on equity (ROE), Profit After Tax (PAT), Earnings Per Share (EPS) to mention a few. However, researchers are beginning to find other measurement of bank performance as the traditional measurements do not meet the needs and interest of other groups other than shareholders and prospective investors (Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN], 2013). A more modern method is the use of the balance score card, which identifies other qualitative measures like customers, internal business operations, learning, and growth as indicators of organisational performance. Munir, Ramzan, Igbal, Ahmad, and Raza (2012); Masud and Haq (2016) identified additional key quantitative performance indicators of banks as total assets, advances, investment, and deposits.

2.1.2. Fraud

According to Taiwo et al. (2016), fraud is defined as an act of dishonesty that results in the loss of property or other legal rights for an individual or an organisation. Nwankwo (2013) stated that fraud is a purposeful behaviour that causes financial losses for an economy or a corporation. Mawutor et al. (2019) define fraud as the deliberate or negligent representation of a materially falsehood that is accepted by the victim and exploited against them.

According to Kparobo (2023), fraudulent conduct is one of the main problems preventing the Nigerian banking sector from operating effectively. A few examples of fraudulent

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activities include poor bookkeeping practices, nonperforming insider-related credits, financial reporting errors, inadequate debt recovery, a disregard for banking laws, rules, and regulations, declining asset quality and the resulting high provisioning requirements, and significant exposure to the capital market through share and margin loans.

There are several ways that bank theft might manifest itself, from minor cash or cheque theft to more serious ones. According to NDIC data, common bank frauds that affect deposits include the presentation of phoney checks, customer credit suppression, ATM fraud, fraudulent transfers and withdrawals, employee theft, and internet banking fraud (Okoye et al., 2024). In line with scope of this study, bank fraud was looked at from the angle amount and involvement. There fraud was measured in terms of total fraud amount, total number of reported cases of fraud and the number of staff involved in fraud,

Total Fraud Amount

This is the real amount of money lost to fraud as a result of various fraudulent behaviours. Evidence from the NDIC Report (2006-2020) that the amount of fraud rose until 2015 and 2016, when it sharply decreased as a result of the anti-fraud measures implemented by the CBN and NDIC. However, in from 2016-2020 there was high incidence of fraud, which signals that the policies by the regulatory authorities lacks the needed solution to significantly reduced the amount of fraud. This could also stem from there

difference ways and means fraud is been perpetrated in banks.

Number of Reported Cases of Fraud

According to Sections 35 and 36 of the NDIC Act of 2006, banks are required to provide the corporation with information on fraud and forgeries, staff terminations, and appointments that are terminated because of fraud. Even while armed robberies and other financial crimes are becoming more prevalent in the media and daily newspapers, the percentage of bank fraud cases that are covered in the newspapers only makes up a small number of bank fraud incidents (Taiwo et al., 2016). Some banks choose to ignore such incidents because they don't think it's appropriate to report them. According to reports by Muritala et al. (2017), Ogbeide (2018), and Taiwo et al. (2016), just one act has an impact on the bank's performance.

In literature there is an on-going argument on the impact of reporting fraud cases on performance of deposit money banks. The first proponents opine that reporting cases of bank fraud would positive improve the performance of deposit money bank (Offiong et al., 2016; Taiwo et al., 2016). Thereby increasing shareholders confidence on the bank. However, Muritala et al. (2016) and Ogbeide (2018), are the opinion that reporting fraud cases have substantial detrimental effect of on DMB performance, They further added that the return on assets will eventually decline, which would lower the value of shareholders.

Total Number of Staff Involved in Fraud

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A perpetrator of fraud must possess the necessary information and abilities, including a thorough understanding of the system that the fraudulent conduct will be carried out on (Wolfe & Hermerson, 2004 as quoted in Dorminey, Fleming, Kranacher & Riley, 2012). There is no question that the number of bank employees engaged in fraud and forgery is constantly rising. Conversely, banks' reluctance to notify and prosecute employees engaged in fraudulent activities may be the reason for the rise in the number of fraud-related staff members (Taiwo et al., 2016). Instead of filing a formal report as required by the NDIC, some bank management may choose to handle the problem internally.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

The topic of fraud has a number of theoretic, ranging from Other studies have conceptualised fraud using a variety of theoretical frameworks, including Donald Cressy's Fraud Triangle theory, Wolfe and Hermerson's Fraud Diamond theory, and Edwin Sutherland's differential theory. This study adopted the fraud triangle theory. It also happens to be the most popular theory. It was predicated on a model created by criminologist and sociologist Donald Cressey, who examined the conduct of white collar crime in the 1950s with regard to those he referred to as trust violators.

Cressey (1973) asserts that the presence of any one of these three factors—pressure (motivation), opportunity, and justification—increases the likelihood of dishonest behaviour. According to this theory, people who violate trust are those who think they have a non-transferable

financial issue and are aware that it may be resolved behind closed doors by betraying the position of financial trust.

2.3. Empirical Review

Funmi, Ojeme and Olusegun (2024) examined the effect of fraud practices on the stability of deposit money banks in Nigeria from the period of from 2009 to 2023. The ex post facto research design was adopted and data was gotten from Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) and Global Financial Data Bulletin annual reports. Autoregressive distributed lag was the estimating method employed (ARDL) to employed to test the hypotheses of the study. It was discovered that the value of fraud has a short- and long-term detrimental but considerable impact on the stability of Nigeria's deposit money banks. On the other hand, in the medium and long terms, the quantity and frequency of fraud cases have a small but favourable impact on the stability of Nigeria's deposit money institutions.

Akande et al (2024) investigated the effect of fraud on financial performance in Nigerian banks for the period 2002 to 2016. The study adopted the ex post factor research design and data was gotten from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical Bulletin and NDIC annual reports. The ordinary least squares was employed to test the hypotheses of the study. The result identified the amount involved in fraud to have positively affected the banking sector performance. While the total number of fraud cases have no significant impact on banking sector performance.

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Jolaiya (2024) investigated the effect of electronic fraud on the financial performance of banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to investigate the effect of electronic fraud through online web transactions, evaluate the effect of electronic fraud through automated teller machine, to determine the effect of fraud through point of sale machine, and to investigate the effect of fraud through mobile phone USSD transactions on the financial performance of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. Panel Generalized method of moments (GMM) was used to analyze the panel series of the model. The Hausman test indicated the random effect model as most fit for the estimation. The major findings of the study revealed that fraud through the automated teller machine (AEF) has significant negative impact on the financial performance of the deposit money banks in Nigeria. The panel regression result also revealed that fraud through the mobile phone channel (MPEF), and fraud through the online banking channel (OBEF) had significant negative effect on the financial performance of the banks studied.

Patricia et al. (2023) assessed how fraud affected Nigerian banks' operational performance. The research also identifies the typical forms of bank fraud that are often committed in Nigerian DMBs, the root causes, degree of employee engagement, impact, prevention and control, and banking performance. In this study, four (4) DMBs in Nigeria were investigated using a causal research design. The results showed that fraud substantially influences ROE and ROA. As a result, it is advised that the NDIC and the CBN

take the necessary steps to prevent fraud from increasing and to maintain system integrity.

Kparobo (2023) looked at how fraud affected Nigerian financial institutions' stability during the previous ten (10) years. While bank stability (BSTA) was used to reflect the stability of financial institutions, IFR, PBP, FRL, and MOL were used to show fraud. The research utilized seven banks that are in Abraka, Ethiopia East. The primary data was acquired via a questionnaire, while the secondary data was derived from bank financial statements spanning the years 2013 to 2022. The statistical software for social sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the coded answer in conjunction with the financial data of the banks that were the subject of the study. The findings demonstrated the detrimental and statistically significant effects of improper financial reporting, subpar bookkeeping procedures, fraudulent loans, and money laundering on the soundness of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Manyo et al (2023) examined the effect of fraud on bank performance in Nigeria. The study adopted the expost facto research design and data was gotten from Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) Annual Report and CBN Statistical Bulletin from 1994 to 2020. Statistical methods such as descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation and OLS regression techniques were employed in the evaluation of the data. The result of the hypotheses revealed number of fraud cases as well as the total amount lost to fraud had a positive and significant impact on bank performance while the total number of staff

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involved in fraud was found to be negative and significant on deposit money banks performance in Nigeria.

Tega and David (2021) examined the impact of fraud on financial performance of deposit money banks: Evidence from Nigeria. The main aim of the study is to investigate if variables like computer fraud, managers looting; inappropriate auditing, peer group pressure affect bank performance. To achieve this objective, research questions and hypotheses were formulated and variables were proxied for fraud and deposit banks performance as distilled from related literatures. The GLS result was used to test the formulated hypotheses with a standard z-value of 1.96. The GLS regression results revealed that there are negative relationships between bank frauds and performance while the z-test shows that bank frauds affect deposit money bank performance in Nigeria.

Odo and Ugwu (2020) evaluated the contribution of creative accounting practices on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. Judgmental random sampling technique was employed to select four banks out of 21 deposit money banks in Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 60 respondents that were chosen through stratified random sampling technique. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze hypotheses one and two in which responses to the questionnaire in 5 points Likert Scale were clustered into two groups. Correlation technique was adopted in analysis of hypothesis

three. The results of the analyses showed that creative accounting contributes significantly to non-financial and financial performance of banks in Nigeria. Also revealed was high correlation between contribution of creative accounting practices on financial and non-financial performance of banks.

Nwobia et al (2020) examined the effect of electronic fraud on performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this research work are to analyse the relationship between ATM fraud and performance of DMBs in Nigeria and to evaluate the relationship between POS fraud and performance of DMBs in Nigeria. The data collected were analyzed using basic descriptive ordinary least square (OLS) and multivariate regression panel data setting with econometric analyses. The results showed negative and insignificant relationship between electronic fraud channels and financial performance variables.

Kolapo and Olaniyan (2018) investigated the impact of fraud on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria between the periods from 1994 to 2015. The Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator was employed to analyze the data. This study showed that the amounts involved in fraud cases, amount lost to fraud and number of staffs involved in fraud have a negative and significant influence on the deposit of banks in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the past value of bank deposit has a positive and significant relationship with deposit of banks in Nigeria. Muoghalu et al (2018) examined the

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effect of electronic banking related fraud on automated teller machines, mobile banking, point of sale terminals and web to return on assets, return on equity, interest income and non-interest income of deposit money banks. Comprehensive data on fraud on the various electronic banking channels from the apex regulatory agency of the banking system: Central Bank of Nigeria began in 2013 thus limiting the study to a period of four years. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was applied in estimating the regression equation, whereas effect of fraud on various channels of electronic banking and financial performance ascertained with the help of the granger causality analysis. The findings from the study dispelled that fraud on point of sale terminals has significant negative effect on interest income, while fraud on automated teller machines, mobile banking and web had no effect on return on assets, return on equity and non-interest income of banks.

3. Methodology

In conducting this study, secondary data sourced from the annual report of Nigeria Deposit Insurance Commission (NDIC) was used. The ordinary least squares were employed in this study to test the hypotheses. The diagnostic test such as multicollinearity, constant residual error, serial correlation, model specification and normality test was carried out and the results were all favourable to the course of study. The

data employed for the period spans from 2006 through 2022. The analysis was conducted using the E-Views 12 statistical package.

3.1 Model Specification

The objective of the study is to investigate the impact of fraud on the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria from 2006 to 2022. Hence, the model for this study adopted the model of Mawutor, Enofe and Embele (2019) and can be stated as:

$$TBD = f(TFA, NRC, TSI) \dots\dots\dots ..(i)$$

In econometric form:

$$TBD_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TFA_t + \beta_2 NRC_t + \beta_3 TSI_t + \varepsilon_t \dots\dots\dots ..(ii)$$

Where

TBD = Total Bank Deposit (a proxy for bank performance);

β_0 = Constant;

TFA = Total Fraud Amount;

NRC = Number of Reported Cases;

TSI = Total Number of Bank Staff Involved in Fraud;

$\beta_1; \beta_2; \beta_3$ = Coefficient of explanatory variables

ε = Standard error

t = Time Series

A priori expectations in with extant literature to be $\beta_1 < 0$; $\beta_2 > 0$; $\beta_3 < 0$

3.2. Operationalization of Variables

Table 3.1
Measurement of variable

Variable	Abbreviation	Measurement	<i>A priori</i>
Performance of DMB (Dependent)	TBD	Total Bank Deposit in DMB (i.e, Savings, Term Deposit, Current Deposit and Domiciliary deposit) in a year	Nil
Total Fraud Amount (independent)	TFA	The total amount lost as a result of fraud in a year	-
Number of Reported Cases (independent)	NRC	Total numbers reported cases of fraud in a year	+
Total of Number of Bank Staff Involved (independent)	TSI	Total Number of Bank Staff Involved in Fraud in a year.	-

Source: Author’s Compilation (2025)

4. Data Analysis, Interpretation and Discussion of Findings

In this section the data of the study was analysed, interpreted and discussed. Descriptive Statistics such as mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation was used to summarize the

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Dev	Observations
TBD	19002649	3412273	45503660	11555888	17
TFA	431153.65	4832.000	204652.0	49916.47	17
NRC	41425.47	1193.000	211713.0	67187.35	17

data of the study. Diagnostics test such as (Serial Correlation, Normality, Linearity, Heteroskedasticity and Multicollinearity) were carried out to fulfil the basic assumption of regression. The hypotheses formulated in chapter one is also tested in this chapter.

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TSI	478.4706	231.000	899.000	191.7733	17
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Source: Author’s computation, 2025

Table 4.1 shows a descriptive statistic of variables used in the study. The mean of Total Bank Deposit (TBD) stood at ₦19, 002,649,000. The minimum and maximum value of TBD in the study was ₦3,412,273,000 and ₦45,503,660,000 respectively, with a standard deviation of ₦11,555,888,000 a exhibiting considerable clustering around the mean. The mean of Total Fraud Amount (TFA), Number of

Table 4.2: *Correlation Matrix*

	TBD	TFA	NRC	TSI
TBD	1.000			
TFA	0.5083	1.0000		
NRC	0.8953	0.3943	1.000	
TSI	0.2349	0.5008	0.0064	1.000

Source: Author’s computation, 2025

The linearity of variables (correlation matrix) in Table 3 shows that the variables exhibited both positive relationship. This is seen in the association between TFA and TBD (0.5083), NRC and TBD (0.8953), TSI and TBD (0.2349). The strength of association between variable were above the threshold of 0.80 in the association between NRC and TBD (0.8953), suggesting the presence of the problem of multicollinearity in the predictor variables

Table 4.3: *Variance Inflation Factor*

	Coefficient	Uncentered	Centered
Variable	Variance	VIF	VIF
C	1.2013	8.6822	NA
TFA	989.2243	3.0093	1.6773

Reported Cases (NRC) and Total Staff Involved in fraud (TSI) investigated stood at ₦431, 153,650,000; 41,425 cases reported of fraud reported, and 479 Bank Staff involved in fraud, respectively. The standard deviation of NRC and TSI exhibited considerable clustering around the mean, however, the standard deviation of TFA failed to exhibit considerable clustering around the mean.

(Studenmund, 2014). However, to further validate the veracity of this result, the Variance Inflation Factor test was done.

4.2 Diagnostics Statistics

We carried out various diagnostics test in order to fulfill the basic assumptions of regression. Some of the diagnostics test we did was autocorrelation test, serial correlations test, constant residual error (Heteroskedasticity), normality and model misspecification test.

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NRC	409.0722	1.7642	1.2566
TSI	56601653	10.7859	1.4166

Source: Author’s computation, 2025

To further strengthen the results from correlation matrix on multicollinearity, the variance inflation factor test was done. From the results in table 4.3, it was observed that none of 5

Source: Author’s computation (2025)

The figure shows that our data satisfy the normality assumption of regression, as seen in the kurtosis and skewness value of 1.8347 and 0.0604. This distribution shows that our data series was positively skewed, and the kurtosis which shows the peakedness of the distribution was mesokurtic in nature. These results is in Table 4.4: *Serial Correlation*

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:	
Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags	

the variables tested indicates the presence of multicollinearity as the centered VIF of the variables were all less than 10.

Figure 4.1: Histogram Normality Graph

Series: Residuals	
Sample 2006 2022	
Observations 17	
Mean	-6.03e-10
Median	-441953.3
Maximum	6791598.
Minimum	-7248726.
Std. Dev.	4370718.
Skewness	0.060499
Kurtosis	1.834702
Jarque-Bera	0.972230
Probability	0.615011

tandem with threshold of (-3 to 3) range of Peck, Olsen and Devore (2008) in determining normality of a distribution. Furthermore, the Jarque-Bera statistics test of normality J-B stat = 0.9722, p = 0.6150 was statistically insignificant for all variables at 5%, implying an insignificant departure away from normality (Studenmund, 2014).

F-statistic	1.1010	Prob. F(2,11)	0.3666
Obs*R-squared	2.8355	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.2423

Source: Author’s computation, 2025
 The series correlation assumption was fulfilled using the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation
 Table 4.5: *Constant Residual Error*

(LM) test, $F(2,11) = 1.1010$, $p = 0.3666 > 0.05$ and the null hypothesis of no serial correlation was accepted.

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity			
F-statistic	1.7439	Prob. F(3,13)	0.2074
Obs*R-squared	4.8782	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.1809
Scaled explained SS	1.1906	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.7553

Source: Author’s computation, 2025
 Similarly, the assumption of the constant residual error test - The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey
 Table 4.6: *Model Misspecification*

test of heteroskedacity, $F(3,13) = 1.7439$, $p = 0.2074 > .05$. This implies that the residual error is no constant residual in the series.

Ramsey RESET Test				
Specification: TBD C TFA NRC TSI				
	Value	Df	Probability	
t-statistic	2.5439	12	0.0258	
F-statistic	6.4716	(1, 12)	0.0258	
Likelihood ratio	7.3326	1	0.0068	

4.4.

Source: Author’s computation, 2025
 Lastly, the Ramsey RESET Test was conducted to test for model miss-specification. The result of the analysis revealed the presence of model misspecification, $F(1,12) = 6.4716$, $p = 0.0258 < 0.05$. This implies that our model was correctly specified.

Multivariate Analyses and Hypotheses Testing

Haven fulfilled the basic assumption of regression, the ordinary least squares estimation technique was employed to test the hypotheses stated in the study. Hypotheses of the study were tested at 5% level of significance (that is, if p -value < 0.05 reject H_0 , else do otherwise)

Table 4.7: Inferential Statistics – Ordinary Least Squares

Variables	Dependent variable: TBD			
	B	S.E	t-Stat.	Prob.
Constant	6517949	3465239	1.8809	0.0826
TFA	15.9264	31.4519	0.5064	0.6211
NRC	149.1087	20.2255	7.3723	0.0001**
TSI	11746.8500	7523.41	1.5614	0.1424
R-squared		0.8569		
Adjusted R-squared		0.8239		
Dnrbin-Watson stat		0.9689		
S.E.		4848876.0		
F-statistics		25.9583		
Prob. (F-statistics)		0.0001**		

**significant at 5 per cent level

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

Table 4.4 revealed the results of the ordinary least squares regression for the model of the study. The explanatory variables employed in the study significantly explain the impact of fraud on performance of deposit money bank in Nigeria.

This conclusion was drawn from the result of the ordinary least square regression, F-statistics = 25.9583, $p = 0.0001 < 0.05$. Furthermore, the adjusted R-Squared stood at 0.8239; that is about 82% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable (performance of DMB) is caused by the explanatory variable used in the

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study. While about 18% of the variations are caused by other variables not included in the model but were adequately captured by the standard error of the regression, $SE = 4848876.0$.

4.4.1 Test of Hypotheses of the study

The hypotheses of the study were tested at 5% level of significance (that is, if p -value < 0.05 reject H_0 , else do otherwise).

H_{01} : Total Fraud Amount has no significant influence on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria

From the result in tables 4.7, Total Fraud Amount has no significant influence on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, $\beta_1 = 15.9264$; $SE = 31.4519$, $p = 0.6211 > 0.05$. Therefore, this study accepted the null hypothesis stated on the study.

H_{02} : Number of reported cases of fraud has no significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria

From the result in tables 4.7, Number of reported cases of fraud has positive and significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, $\beta_1 = 149.1087$; $SE = 20.2255$, $p = 0.0001 < 0.05$. Therefore, this study rejected the null hypothesis stated on the study, that Number of reported cases of fraud has no significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H_{03} : Total number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria

From the result in tables 4.7, Total number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria, $\beta_1 = 11746.8500$; $SE = 7523.41$, $p = 0.1424 > 0.05$. Therefore, this study accepted the null hypothesis stated on the study.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The result from the revealed that Total Fraud Amount has no significant influence on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This result implies that total fraud amount has no significant influence on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This result of this study is not consistent with the work of Akande et al (2024) who found that total fraud amount positively affected the banking sector performance. Manyo et al (2023) found that total amount lost to fraud had a positive and significant impact on bank performance. Kolapo and Olaniyan (2018) found that total fraud amount has negative impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Secondly, the study revealed that Number of reported cases of fraud has positive and significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This findings is not consistent with the work of Akande et al (2024) who found that total number of fraud cases have no significant impact on banking sector performance. Manyo et al (2023) also found that total number of fraud cases have no significant impact on banking sector performance. Kolapo and Olaniyan (2018) found that number of

reported cases of fraud has negative impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Lastly, the result of the study revealed that Total number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Manyo et al (2023) found that total number of staff involved in fraud was found to be negative and significant on deposit money banks performance in Nigeria. Also, Kolapo and Olaniyan (2018) found that total number of bank staff involved in fraud has negative impact on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

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The study investigated the impact of fraud on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria from the period of 2006-2022. Flowing from the result of the study, it was concluded that Number of reported cases of fraud has positive and significant effect on performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. While total fraud amount and number of bank staff involved in fraud has no significant impact on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. In line with findings the study, it was recommended that banks should always publish cases of fraud to boost the shareholders confidence in the banks, so as to improve the performance in form of deposit

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Oyewole Johnson Stephen FCA and Eke Robert Ike PhD, FCA.

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Oyewole Johnson Stephen FCA and Eke Robert Ike PhD, FCA.